

Breaking with Misogyny in a Patriarchal Society: The Contribution of Reflective Groups

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Abstract

Inequalities, rooted in notions of division and hierarchy between the sexes—what, in the context of women's struggles, has come to be known as “gender”—underpin a patriarchal society notably marked by violence, sexism, racism, and income inequality. Gender-based violence reveals men's difficulty in breaking away from the power structures that maintain the hegemony of masculinity, with machismo reinforcing behaviors that diminish the feminine and value characteristics associated with men, such as aggression and control. In the context of the 2030 Agenda, SDG 5 (Gender Equality) seeks to eliminate all forms of violence against women and girls. Achieving this goal requires, among other measures, structural and cultural changes through the strengthening of public policies that promote gender equity and deconstruct the violent norms that perpetuate dominant masculinity. In this sense, the objective here is to present data, analyze the legislation created to protect women and punish men in the face of escalating violence, and, above all, consider Gender Reflection Groups as an intervention measure within the network to combat violence against women, in which men are the focus of cultural change in the process of overcoming toxic masculinity.

Background

Gender policy refers to the set of actions and strategies aimed at promoting equality between men and women by addressing gender-based inequalities and violence. This policy manifests itself at various levels, ranging from international agreements and national legislation to local public policies and affirmative action in various sectors.

From a global perspective, SDG 5 of the 2030 Agenda (UN: 2015) aims to eliminate all forms of violence against women and girls, specifically through Target 5.2, which proposes to eradicate all forms of violence in both the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual exploitation. At the national level, laws and public policies – such as the criminalization of gender-based violence, as well as programs to combat domestic violence and promote economic autonomy – are established to guarantee women's rights and promote equality. Locally, gender policies manifest in actions such as the creation of referral centers for women experiencing

violence, the promotion of women's empowerment projects, the guarantee of access to health and education services, and the inclusion of women in political and economic decision-making spaces.

However, there are few initiatives focused on men whose identity, shaped by toxic masculinity[1], proves to be deeply harmful both to themselves and to women. Hence the importance of considering gender reflection groups, which are beginning to gain visibility in a society where women are increasingly occupying social, cultural, professional, and political spaces that were traditionally reserved for men (Palma; Santos Sá: 2011).

Reflection groups are educational and dialogue-based spaces primarily aimed at men who have committed domestic violence, with the goal of fostering accountability and preventing future incidents. They serve as a socio-educational measure to challenge sexist attitudes, explore masculinity, and promote healthy relationships by discussing topics such as the social construction of gender, relationships between men and women, emotional regulation, alcohol and drug use, and legislation protecting women.

This gender literacy brings to mind the challenges posed by the feminist movement, which, in the 1980s and 1990s, sparked research and studies on men and masculinities in both the United States and Europe. Integrated into gender and feminist studies, men are constructed and defined by a gender that shapes bodies according to an established social norm, rather than as universal subjects and representatives of humanity. Men are also addressed by the demands of feminist movements, through various theoretical tensions, as participants in a social structure rife with power relations, privileges, and oppressions (Beiras et al., 2021).

In this context, reactionary masculinity groups have emerged with the aim of maintaining the status quo of male power and challenging progress related to gender equality. Thus, in the 1980s and 1990s, a network of communities with a masculinist and often misogynistic ideology – known as the “macho sphere” – also emerged, promoting a return to traditional gender roles and reacting against feminism and equal rights. The term gained popularity in the late 2000s, reaching a turning point in 2010 as it moved from the fringes to the mainstream of the internet (a virtual ecosystem encompassing forums, YouTube, and Telegram, where influencers promote “alpha” masculinity, focused on strength, money, and the subjugation of women)[2]. These groups, which include movements such as Red Pill[3], advocate for male superiority and domination and spread misogyny and hatred, attracting young people through forums and social media.

Analysis / Findings

The escalation of violence against women worldwide in 2025 reveals a scenario of increasing brutality that manifests itself not only in the frequency of crimes but also in their intimate, symbolic, and cruel nature. According to the Report on Gender-Based Violence in the European Union (FRA, EIGE, Eurostat: 2024)[1], approximately 17% of women have experienced violence at the hands of an intimate partner. About 30% of women in the EU have experienced physical violence or threats and/or sexual violence at some point in their lives. Nearly 13% of women have been victims of physical violence or threats without sexual violence, and 17% have experienced sexual violence.

According to data from the European Parliament (2025; FRA, EIGE, Eurostat: 2024), the EU countries with the highest rates of gender-based violence are: Finland (57% of respondents said they had experienced gender-based violence and 37% had suffered sexual violence), Sweden (52% of female respondents experienced gender-based violence and 41% were victims of sexual violence), and Hungary (49% of female respondents experienced gender-based violence, 17% reported having been subjected to sexual violence, and 31% were victims of physical violence).

With regard to femicide^[2], in the EU, women are killed nearly twice as often as men when the perpetrator is a partner or a family member. Eurostat data show a rate of 4.1 women killed per million people, compared to 2.2 men. Latvia consistently recorded the highest femicide rate across the bloc in 2022 and 2023 (approximately 17 women per million people). Lithuania had the second-highest rate in both years, with 10 women per million people, followed by Austria with nearly five in 2022 and 2023. Globally, Africa stands out as the continent with the highest femicide rate—30 per million people—and the highest absolute number of victims: an estimated 22,600 in 2024. The Americas and Oceania also recorded high rates of family- or partner-related femicides in 2024 (15 and 14 per million, respectively), while rates were lower in Asia with seven victims and on the European continent overall with five victims (Dell'Anna; Yilmaz: 2025).

In Brazil, according to data from the study “Elas Vivem: a urgência da vida” by the Security Observatories Network, which monitored nine Brazilian states throughout the year, approximately 12 women were victims of some form of violence every 24 hours in 2025. According to the survey, 4,558 women were victimized, representing a 9% increase compared to 2024. Among the types of violence recorded, the rise in cases of sexual violence and rape stood out. Reports increased by 56.6%, rising from 602 to 961 cases. The profile of the victims reveals an alarming scenario: 56.5% were children and adolescents between the ages of 0 and 17 (Ramos: 2025).

The Brazil that emerges from the data in this report is not only unequal; it is lethal for women. From femicides disguised as other forms of violence – from Amazonas to Rio de Janeiro – and across all records of violence, the structure of hatred is omnipresent. In Bahia and Ceará, lives are cut short under the banal pretext of jealousy or unrequited breakups. In Maranhão and Piauí, the absence of protective measures for most victims exposes a state that arrives too late. Worse still: in Pernambuco and Pará, sexual violence preys on the bodies of girls who have not even left childhood behind. The Report exposes the failure of a protection network that, until it becomes territorial and intersectional, will continue to allow barbarism to be the rule, not the exception – even in the face of the National Pact to Combat Femicide, launched in February 2026 by the federal government, which has yet to present immediate measures (Ramos: 2025).

According to the Brazilian Forum on Public Safety (FBSP: 2026), 1,568 women were victims of femicide in the country in 2025, a 4.7% increase from the previous year. Since the criminalization of femicide^[3], at least 13,703 women have been murdered simply because they are women. The data reflects the number of police reports filed by Civil Police departments across the country that have classified these cases as femicide (FBSP, 2026). However, most cases currently classified as such by the police stem from intimate partner violence, with contempt and discrimination against women being factors that security forces are often unable to recognize. Although the data has been increasing year by year, it is likely that the actual numbers are higher than can be measured.

Faced with this reality, preventing and combating violence against women requires action on multiple fronts. Among these measures, one option is to address gender literacy among male perpetrators, which could help curb the escalation of violence against women.

The Maria da Penha Law and Reflective groups

In supporting victims of violence, the Maria da Penha Law[4] provided for assistance to women through social assistance services, the Unified Health System, and the Unified Public Security System; it introduced changes to the procedural process, simplifying procedures, expediting the handling of cases of this nature, and establishing new means for conflict resolution, such as the application of protective measures, including, most recently, the participation of the perpetrator in rehabilitation and re-education programs, as well as psychosocial support for perpetrators of domestic violence (Azevêdo; Pastre: 2024).

By proposing to work directly with the perpetrators of violence, Law No. 11,340/2006 highlights the need for awareness-raising efforts, underscoring the inadequacy of the criminal justice system as the sole measure involving these men, who are perpetrators of violence against women. Mostly referred to as Reflective Groups, these groups must be educational and mandatory, as provided by law[5], and are, for the most part, grounded in feminist theory and gender theory. Their main focus is to bring about a change in the values and behaviors of men who commit acts of aggression regarding violence against women. They function as a process of re-education and a way to address the perpetrator (Prates; Andrade, 2013).

Reflection groups for perpetrators of violence differ from general masculinity groups. Linked to judicial bodies, the Reflection Groups with Men Perpetrators of Violence (GHAV) are aimed at men who have not voluntarily engaged in a process of rethinking their masculinity. In contrast, general masculinity groups are attended by individuals who are already aware of such processes. Both, however, can run in parallel, producing diverse connections, provided they are committed to gender equity and human rights, without restricting themselves to essentialisms or cliques that lack empathy toward the opposite gender. In this sense, the proposal is to break the silence and promote conversations about vulnerability, fatherhood, sexuality, and the construction of new masculinities[6].

The first known intervention program for men who commit domestic violence was launched in 1977 in Boston, USA, under the name EMERGE. Some time later, in 1981, Duluth, Minnesota, USA, developed the Domestic Abuse Intervention Project (DAIP), which, in partnership with the judiciary, began working to ensure the safety of victims of abuse and hold perpetrators accountable. In the 1980s, the program spread across North America, Europe, Australia, and Latin America. Initially, the programs were run by volunteers, but over time, links were established with the judicial system, which, in turn, began to include in its sentences the requirement that men who commit domestic violence participate in such programs. In Latin America, Argentina was the first country to create intervention groups, but today there are established programs in several countries, including Brazil (Azevêdo; Pastre: 2024).

In Brazil, the first programs focused on perpetrators of domestic violence emerged in the 1990s. Pioneering initiatives in this field included those of the non-governmental organization Pró-Mulher, Família e Cidadania in São Paulo and the Instituto Noos in Rio de Janeiro. Other non-governmental organizations that work or have worked with male clients are also noteworthy. In Pernambuco: the PAPAI Institute in Recife; in Rio de Janeiro:

the Promundo Institute; in São Paulo: Ecos: Communication on Sexuality and the now-defunct CES – Center for Health Education and Pró-Mulher Família e Cidadania (founded in the 1990s); and in Belo Horizonte: the Albam Institute and, more recently, the Casa da Palavra Institute highlight positive results from initiatives that incorporate a gender and masculinities approach for men.

Between November 2013 and February 2014, the Noos Institute, in partnership with PROMUNDO, conducted a survey of group-based intervention services for men who commit violence against women and identified 25 such programs across various Brazilian states. Regarding these identified programs, 21.1% began their intervention activities with perpetrators of violence between 1999 and 2002, 36.8% between 2003 and 2011, and 31.6% after 2012. Furthermore, it was found that the institutions responsible for the programs are predominantly governmental (68.4%), followed by nongovernmental organizations (21.1%), and 10.5% are partnerships between governmental and nongovernmental entities (Azevêdo & Pastre, 2024).

In 2021, the Federal University of Santa Catarina published a national map of these initiatives on its website. There are numerous programs or groups for men who commit domestic violence against women, with a total of 312 initiatives across Brazil. Specifically, 25 groups were identified in the North, 42 in the Midwest, 54 in the Northeast, 65 in the Southeast, and 126 in the South of the country, with 50 of these initiatives operating in the state of Paraná, a pioneer in this field (Beiras; Martins; Sommarive; Huggill: 2020).

The number of groups identified per state may vary due to numerous factors. The study was coordinated by the state-level offices responsible for assisting women in situations of domestic and family violence, and, in each locality, there was greater or lesser availability of time on the part of the person assigned to the task, greater or lesser ease of communication between the appellate courts (Tribunals) and the trial courts (Courts), in addition to the fact that some states already had policies in place on the subject, while others were still in the early stages of working with the groups.

The Public Prosecutor's Office and the Judiciary play an important role in the smooth progress of interventions, according to the study. The activities carried out by the groups are quite diverse in form and in the circumstances under which participants are referred (sentence, protective measure, flagrante delicto, non-compliance with protective measures, through the network, on a voluntary basis, or as a condition for conditional suspension of proceedings), revealing that training processes are sometimes disorganized and tailored to each initiative and professional, with varying numbers of sessions and their frequency, ranging from a single session in the form of a lecture to 16 sessions held weekly, biweekly, or monthly. Furthermore, the topics addressed and the approaches taken with the groups also vary (Azevêdo; Pastre: 2024, p. 78).

Despite the challenges, it is evident that group work with men has the potential to bring about personal and relational changes, fostering more equitable and healthier relationships between men and women, as well as between men and the world at large. Reflection groups open up possibilities for building more equitable gender relations. Some studies indicate extremely low recidivism rates. Projects such as the Men's Education and Accountability Service (SerH) in Rio de Janeiro have reduced the recidivism rate of violence to about 1.5%, much lower than rates without educational intervention (Freire: 2025).

In this sense, while reactionary masculinity groups work to maintain the status quo of male power, questioning progress related to gender equity and generating even more violence against women, gender reflection

groups seek to deconstruct a singular, hegemonic masculinity by considering the plurality of expressions of masculinities, as well as relationships with women and femininities, from a relational perspective of historical analysis, social critique, and the pursuit of a more just and diverse society for all people.

Policy Recommendations

- **Education and Awareness:** Invest in education by developing educational programs designed to challenge sexist beliefs and promote gender equality starting in childhood.
- **Male Engagement:** Create a basic model for men’s reflection groups to facilitate widespread adoption, given the slow pace of implementation as a public policy.
- **Professional Training:** Implement effective public policies for training professionals in key areas, such as public safety; education; social services; municipal police; nursing; the Public Prosecutor’s Office; representatives of the Judiciary; and lawyers.
- **Political Commitment:** Develop strategies, supported by a collective and intersectoral commitment, capable of breaking the historical cycle of violence.
- **Political and Legal Action:** Criminalize and strictly punish femicide and gender-based violence, treating misogyny as a non-bailable and imprescriptible crime, in accordance with Bill 896/2026.
- **Specialized Shelter:** Create private spaces such as the “lilac room” to prevent revictimization, offering psychological, legal, and social assistance support.
- **Ensure the effectiveness of Emergency Protective Measures (MPUs),** based on the Maria da Penha Law, to stop physical, psychological, moral, financial, or sexual violence.
- **Implement the Maria da Penha patrol programs** with the aim of monitoring compliance with protective measures.
- **Economic Independence:** Ensuring equal pay and financial autonomy for women, breaking the cycle of dependence and submission.

Conclusion

The connection between violence and masculinities has become an important area of study, as it is now understood as a category that provides insight into the expression of masculinity and male identity in many societies. Gender-based violence reveals the difficulty men face in breaking away from the power structures that maintain the hegemony of masculinity.

By viewing misogyny as a deeply rooted structure that organizes society and dictates power hierarchies, we begin to confront it as a collective challenge requiring mobilization, public pressure, and cultural change to

transform patriarchal logic. In this sense, breaking with misogyny in a patriarchal society requires collective action to dismantle structures of hatred and inequality, specifically the structure of the “macho sphere.” This involves criminalizing gender-based violence, ensuring women’s economic independence, promoting egalitarian education from childhood onward, and engaging men in the fight against structural machismo.

With this goal in mind, the municipality of Conceição do Mato Dentro, through the Department of Women’s Affairs[1], aims to establish the Gender Reflection Group as a key mechanism in combating violence against women and girls in the municipality. In partnership with the Casa da Palavra Institute and with the support of the Public Prosecutor’s Office, the Judiciary, the Civil Police Station, and other directly involved stakeholders, a space for “listening” and “rebuilding life trajectories” is currently being established, with the aim of fostering attitudinal change through reflection and education.

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Notes

[1] Toxic masculinity refers to a set of cultural norms that impose on men the idea that they must be strong, aggressive, and dominant, and that they must suppress their emotions. This harms not only women but also men themselves, leading to problems such as isolation, violence, mental health issues, and dysfunctional relationships, as it denies vulnerability and feelings such as empathy and fear, which are associated with weakness.

[2] Louis Theroux's documentary "Inside the Machosphere" shows how this movement has gained global reach, advocating for the subjugation of women and the dominance of patriarchy, while also flirting with extremist rhetoric, including anti-Semitism. While contextualizing the rise of these figures, the documentary filmmaker paints a consistent portrait of their audience and raises an inevitable question: the digital environment has become fertile ground for the spread of ideas that often border on criminality. Available on Netflix. <https://www.netflix.com/search?q=machosfer&jbv=81920687>. Gradually, as they are deemed criminals, these creators of misogynistic content are being banned from the online space.

[3] Members of the Red Pill movement (a reference to the 1999 film *The Matrix*), who call themselves coaches or influencers of masculinity, view the world "with awareness and without frills," as one unjustly dominated by women. In their distorted view, gender equality has already been achieved, and today, feminists are responsible for spreading hatred against the male population. They propose sticking to "natural" roles, with women exercising their gift of motherhood, caring, being gentle, and nurturing, and men, that of guiding and being the foundation of the home, ignoring the world around them that is undergoing a tremendous revolution. There is, therefore, a crisis of masculinity, and those who cannot cope with women's autonomy and social transformations resort to machismo to reaffirm their virility. In the face of the spread of hate speech, a social and political movement is growing in the country (including legislative proposals) that seeks to criminalize misogyny and hold accountable those who create content that incites violence against women.

[4] The data was collected between September 2020 and March 2024 by the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights and the European Institute for Gender Equality, revealing the experiences of women in the 27 EU countries based on interviews with 114,023 women aged 18 to 74.

[2] Defined by the UN as an intentional homicide motivated by gender-related factors: for example, unequal power relations, gender stereotypes, or harmful social norms that can place women in a more vulnerable position. UN Women. Five essential facts to know about femicide. Available <https://www.unwomen.org/en/articles/explainer/five-essential-facts-to-know-about-femicide#:~:text=Fe-micide:%20definition%20and%20causes,viole%20harmful%20practices%20and%20trafficking>. Accessed on March 15, 2026.

[3] The criminalization of femicide in Brazil, introduced by Law 13,104/2015 and updated by Law 14.994/2024, classifies homicide as a heinous crime when committed against women for gender-based reasons. It is defined as domestic or family violence or contempt or discrimination against women, with penalties ranging from 20 to 40 years of imprisonment. Femicide is considered a crime arising from the victim's female gender, whether in the context of domestic and family violence or in other contexts of contempt or discrimination against women.

[4] Law No. 11,340, dated August 7, 2006, is recognized by the United Nations as the third-best law in the world for combating violence against women—second only to the Spanish and Chilean laws. It establishes mechanisms to curb domestic and family violence against women, pursuant to § 8 of Article 226 of the Federal Constitution, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, and the Inter-American Convention on the Prevention, Punishment, and Eradication of Violence against Women; provides for the creation of Courts for Domestic and Family Violence against Women; amends the Code of Criminal Procedure, the Penal Code, and the Law on the Execution of Criminal Sentences; and makes other provisions. Brasília/DF: Presidency of the Republic, 2006. Available at: http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/-ato2004-2006/2006/lei/l11340.htm. Accessed on March 15, 2026.

[5] These rehabilitation programs aim to promote accountability and prevent future crimes. Pursuant to Articles 22, 35, and 45 of Law No. 11,340/2006, judges may order mandatory attendance at sessions where facilitators address issues of masculinity, gender, and human rights. In collaboration, the National Council of Justice, through Recommendation No. 124 of January 7, 2022, resolves in its Article 1 “To recommend that the State Courts of Justice establish and maintain programs aimed at fostering reflection and raising awareness among perpetrators of domestic and family violence, with the objective of enforcing the emergency protective measures provided for in subparagraphs VI and VII of the Maria da Penha Law.”

[6] The documentary “The Silence of Men” (2019), produced by Papo de Homem and Instituto PdH, explores how upbringings rooted in machismo, toxic masculinity, and emotional repression (“men don’t cry”) affect women’s mental health, relationships, and safety. Based on research involving more than 40,000 people, the film seeks to break the silence and promote conversations about vulnerability, fatherhood, sexuality, and the construction of new masculinities. Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NRom49UVXCE>. Accessed on March 24, 2026.

[7] Of the 853 municipalities in Minas Gerais, Conceição do Mato Dentro is the 11th to establish a dedicated department for women. As part of its 20 monthly protective measures, the first initiative of the Municipal Department for Women (SMM) was to establish the Specialized Reference Center for Assistance to Women in Situations of Violence (CREAM), with the Reflective Group serving as one of its programs. Along with these measures, Mayor Otacílio Neto Costa Mattos approved the construction of the Conceição Women’s House as a structural project, a model adapted from the Women Living Without Violence Program. The center

will bring together, in a single location, specialized services for multidisciplinary care, shelter, the Maria da Penha Patrol, and psychosocial support. With a focus on intersectorality, these smaller units integrate health, social assistance, security, and justice services. They include shelter and triage, psychosocial support, a police station, a magistrate's court, the Public Prosecutor's Office, the Public Defender's Office, promotion of economic autonomy, and a playroom.

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